

Influence of Parental Career and Education on Conduct Disorder Among Young Adults

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Abstract

The study examined the influence of parental career and Education on conduct Disorder among young Adults. A total of 98 participants consisting of 48 males and 50 females with age average of 13 and 20 participated in the study. Their mean age was 15.30 and standard deviation age was 3.48. The participants were youth/young adults attending extra moral lesson at Nnebuisi Area Asaba and Ubulu-Uku all in Delta State, Nigeria. The instrument used for the study was developed by Uria (2000) based on parental career on conduct Disorder (PCCD). Choas (2001) found the scale to have total cronbach alpha of .64 to .71 the instrument was made up of 5 likert typed scale, with 24 items. The design of the study was a survey typed and 2 way ANOVA statistics was used in the data analysis. It was shown that significant differences existed in the manifestations of conduct disorder in both careers and educational variables. However, no interaction effect of the career and education on conduct disorder was observed. Implications and recommendations of the finding were made in the line with the results obtained.

Key words: Parental Career; Education; Conduct Disorder, Young Adults

Introduction

Parental career and education as they say has a very important role to play in the lives of children and young adults in the family as regards to their conducts or behaviour. This is in view of the fact that educational background of the parents has a lot of impacts in the lives of their children and young adults either positively or negatively. It is said that most educated parents are more likely to nurture young adults whose behaviour are more decent than the young adults with in decant behaviours. For instance, a reputable educated parent in the society who engage in a good white collar jobs or careers often nurture children and young adults of decent behaviour as they are more persuaded to enroll their wards in the most reputable and discipline schools where they will be thought in order to boost their psychological satisfaction and social status.

These children and young adults as a result of their parental background earned to follow suit with their parents demands.

This is against the background of the poor parents who are not too educated and engage in some menial task job or careers like labourers, hawkers commercial bus drivers or petty traders whose children and young adult are not well taken care of eventually falls into a notorious gang in the society with all sorts of conduct disorder as a result of their parents social status (Lisa, 1984). This social status of the parents may often times deny them opportunity to interact with their children and young adults, this is more significant among the petty traders and menial job workers than the vocational and service workers who are likely to have more chance to visit and always at their homes often and interact with their children and young adults. On this basis therefore, it is imperative to encourage education among parents in order to secure jobs that will afford them the opportunity to closely Monitor their children. Education is simply one aspect of socialization which involves acquisition of knowledge and learning of skills whether intentionally or unintentionally, it often helps to shape Even beliefs and moral values of the people. There is no doubt that the educated parents are more likely to nurture children with good moral behaviour or conduct than those that are not educated.

Statement of the Problem

Parental profession and education has been identified to have a serious influence in the behaviour modification of the children and young adults, this is aided by the social structure of the society which grouped individuals into various classes. Those who are not well educated are often denied the opportunity to have a good job or career, while the educated elites always finds their way to better profession, which invariably contribute to conduct status of their children and young adults. This study is fashioned to determine why there is variation in young adults conducts among the families. Other problem includes the reason behind parent's inability to adopt the use of favourable parental control to their young adult. Based on this, the questions posed by the research includes.

1. Will there be a significant difference in the manifestation of conduct disorder among the three domains of profession?
2. Will the young adult of non-educated parent exhibit conduct disorder more than those of educated parents?
3. Will there be any interaction of career and education on conduct disorder?

Theoretical Framework

At the beginning of the 18th century, children and young adult were viewed as non-person. They did not receive special treatment or recognition. Discipline then is what we now call abuse. These were some assumptions about life. The first assumption was that life was hard and you had to survived. The people of that time in history did not have the convenience that we take for granted. For example, the medical practices of those days were primitive in comparison to

present day medicine, marriages were more or convenience rather than for childbearing or romance.

The second assumption was that infants and child mortality were high. It did not make sense to the parents in those days to create an emotional bond with children. There was a strong chance that children and young adults would not survive until full adulthood and maturity.

At the end of 18th century, “the Enlightenment” appeared as a new cultural transition. There was a huge increase in the amount of movable goods were easy to steal. The stealing of these goods made property crime to rise tremendously in the urban centers, the wealth of the upper class increased, and stealing become a way of living. These large urban centers also created another problem. The work place was now separated from the home. During the hard times both parents took jobs, there was also very little for the young adults to do, especially when school was not in session. It was then that young adults were becoming increasingly unsupervised. These young adults were largely unemployed the huge influx of people to these urban areas overwhelmed the society. The factories could not keep up and unemployment becomes a factor, poverty becomes widespread (John, 1995).

Therefore, the concept delinquency can be strictly define as conduct that is out to accord with accepted behaviour of the law, with respect to adolescents, delinquent behaviour is harder to define, because there is no consensus regarding exactly what behaviours constitutes delinquency or problem. Young adult or adolescent is a period of greatest risk for violation of the law, part of the reason for this, is because some violations (status offenses) are limited to minors. That is the behaviour that constitutes status offense are not violation of the law when perpetrated by an adult.

Even when status offenses are discounted in research, young adult is the time when violation of the law is most likely to occur (McCord, 1993).

Social scientists have speculated on the cause of delinquency for two hundred years. They have organized observed facts about delinquents’ behaviours into complete theoretical models. Biosocial theories seek to explain the onset of delinquent behaviours such as aggression and violence, from the stand point of the physical qualities of the offenders. Though many of these criminologists have medical or natural science background, a number are a convert from the social tradition. The origin of this school of thought is generally credited to the Italian physician Cesare Lombroso (1865 - 1909) known as the father of criminology. Lombroso put his many years of medical research to use in his theory of criminal that make the biological and physiological similar to our primitive ancestors. These atavistic individual are savage throw back to an earlier state of human evolution. Due to this link, the “born criminal” has such physical traits as enormous jaws, strong caving, a flattened nose and supplementary teeth. Lombroso makes such statements as it was easy to understand why the inner turmoil during which they examine their values and make decision about life role. Using Erickson’s approach, (he behavior of young adult

or youthful drug abusers might be viewed as an expression of confusion over their place in the society. Their inability to direct behaviour towards useful outlets and perhaps their dependency on others offer them solutions to their problem. Psychoanalyst such as David Abrahamsen view delinquents as id-dominated people who suffer from the inability to control impulsive, pleasure seeking drives perhaps because they suffered unhappy experiences in childhood or had care, delinquents suffer from weak or damage egos that make them unable to cope with the conventional societies psychiatrist Symorhallack, views delinquency as a manifestation of feeling of oppression and the inability of youths to strive by producing positive psyche results helping them to feel free and independent, giving them, the possibility of excitement and the chance to use their skill and imagination, providing the problem of positive gain, allowing them a change to rationalize their own sense of failure.

Based on the works of the American Psychologist John B. Watson (1878 - 1958) and popularized by Harvard professor B.F skinner, (1904 - 1990). Behaviourism concerns itself solely with measurable events and not the unobservable psychic phenomenon described by psychoanalysts. Behaviourist suggests that individual(s) learn by observing how people react to their behavior. Behaviour is triggered initially by a stimulus or change in the environment. If a particular behavior that are not reinforced or punished will be extinguished or become extinct. Therefore, some behaviourist holds that a person's learning and social experiences, coupled with his or her values and expectations, determine behaviour. This is known as social learning approach. Albert Bandura, (1965) hold that children learn their behavior in accordant to the reaction they received; the behaviour of those adults they are in close contact with especially parents; and the behavior they view on television and in movies.

Bandura (1965) also suggested that adolescent aggression is as a result of disrepute dependency relation with parents. This refers to frustration and anger a child feels when parents provide poor role models and hold back affection and nurturing. He states "a child who lacks close dependent ties to his parents can have little opportunity or desire to model himself after and to internalize their standards of behaviour. In the absence of such internalized controls, the child's aggression is likely to be exposed in an immediate, direct and socially unacceptable Fashions" (P. 52).

Drever's version of control theory was first articulated in his famous book "causes of delinquency" (1969) links behaviour to the bond an individual maintains with the society. When that bond weakens or breaks, the constructs that society put on its members are lifted, and an individual may violate the law Drever control theory assumes that all individual are potential delinquents and criminals (born) that social controls, not moral values maintain law and order without control and in the absence of sensitivity to and interest in others, a youth is free to comment criminal act (P. 205).

Drever speculates that a constituent value system exists and that all people in society are exposed to it, delinquents defy his moral code because their attachment to society is weak. Drever views the young adult violator as someone who rejects social norms and beliefs. The major elements of his arguments are:

- i. There is a "variation in belief in the moral validity of social rules".
- ii. The variation is brought about by a wakening of the attachment of the individual to element of society and
- iii. This condition produces delinquent behaviour.

Psychologically, Beck (1978) in his book title, "Cognitive theory and emotional disorder" focuses on the individuals' thinking as the core determinants of behaviour and effect. There are reciprocal interactions between cognitive, effect behaviour and physiology, but problems are primarily driven and maintained by cognition, problems arise as a result of errors in things. Irrational thinking or belief and conscious cognitive schema, impact how we view the world and ourselves.

Some experts view the cause of delinquency as essentially psychological after all most behaviours labeled delinquent for example violence, theft, social misconduct seen to be symptomatic of some underlying psychological unmet youth have poor lives, destructive relationship with neighbours, friends and teachers and conflicts authority figures, in general these relationship seems to indicate a disturbed personality structure. And since delinquent behaviours occurs among young adults or youths in every racial, ethnic and socio-economic group. Psychologists view it as a function of emotional and mental disturbance, rather than purely as a result of social factors, such as racism, poverty and class conflict. Psychodynamic theory argues that the human personality contains three major components. The id, is the unrestrained, primitive, pleasure seeking component with which each child is born, the ego develops through the reality of living in the world and helps manage and restrains the id's need for mediate gratification. The super-ego develops through interaction with parents and other significant people and represent the development of conscience and the moral rules that are shared by most adults. Psychodynamic theory suggests that unconscious motivations for behaviour come from id's action account for two primary needs such as sex and aggression. Human behaviour is often marked by symbolic actions that reflect hidden feelings, stealing a car may reflect a person's unconscious need for shelter and mobility to escape from hostile enemies or perhaps as urge to enter a closed, dark, world - like that reflects the earliest memories (sex).

In Freud's three psychosexual stages of developmental theory is the phallic stage in which children from 3 to 6 years of age receive pleasure from founding their genitals. During this period, the male child develops great unconscious feeling for his mother (castration anxiety) Oedipus complex and the female child for father (alectra complex) Oedipus complex and the two later stages, genital; and latency but, these are considered less important on human development because for all intents and purposes, the personality is formed at five. Any trauma that occurs during any of these early life states may have a lasting affect on the child's personality. According to psychoanalytic view, the most serious type of youthful anti-social behavior such as murder

might be motivated by psychosis, while neurotic. Feelings would be responsible for less serious delinquent act and status offense, such as petty theft and truancy.

Eric Erickson speculated that many adolescent experience a life crisis in which they feel emotional, impulsive and uncertain of their role and purpose to resolve this crisis. Most youths achieve a sense of ego (identity) a firm sense of who they are and what they stand for. However, some youths cannot adequately deal with their feelings of role conflict and experience a sense of role diffusion, feeling of uncertainty that make them susceptible to suggestion and at the mercy of others who might lead them astray. The clash between ego identity and role diffusion is precipitated by an identity crisis a period of inner turmoil during which they examines their value and make decision about life roles, researches on Juvenile delinquency have focused more on wide range variables. For example various personality characteristics, family relations, and socio-cultural factors have been implicated in the incidence of juvenile and youthful crime. The identification of diverse correlations of delinquency reflects the multidimensional nature of human behavior as well as the different conceptual orientation of the researchers. Although the correlates of delinquency have been widely assessed, few researchers have evaluated the predictors of serious and repeated criminal activity among adolescents because the adolescents and their siblings account for an inordinate percentage of juvenile criminal activity, the identification of such variable is an empirical priority.

Disbon, Sprackhen, Andrews and Patterson (1996), using 186 adolescent boys age 13 - 14 and their friend were videotaped and analysed to understand the processes of influence associated with antisocial behaviour. Sequential analyses revealed a statistically reliable reciprocal pattern between rule breaking, talk and laugh delinquent (both boy's arrested) whereas in the mix (one arrested), reciprocation occurred between normative talk and laugh. Longitudinal analyses of boy's behaviour over 2 years revealed that the deviance training sequence was prognostic increase in self reported delinquent behaviours.

Perkins in a study to examine the organisms behavioural and contextual covariates of risk behaviour among diverse groups of administered Attitude Behaviour Questionnaire (ABO) to sample of 16, 375 adolescent within the ages of 12-17 years at Michigan. In almost all cases, correlates among risk behaviour with the entire sample and within the age, gender and ethnic group were significant, Slowbil (2012) in his research, risk and promotive affect were investigated as predictors of persistent serious delinquency in the Alabama youth study living in different neighbourhoods, participants closes studies of ages 13-17 years for older. Sample and 7-13 years for the younger samples. Risks and promotive affects were studies in sex domains: child behaviour, child attitude, school and leisure activities, family functioning and demographics. Regression models improved when promotive affects were included with risk effect in predicting persistent serious delinquency. Disadvantage neighbourhoods, compared with better neighbourhood had a higher prevalence of risk affects and a lower prevalence or promotive

affect. However, predictive relationship between risk and promotive effect were linear and similar across neighbourhood and socio-economic status.

Method

Participants

Ninety-eight (98) participants drawn from young adults attending extra moral lessons at Nnebuisi road Asaba and Ubulu-Uku Delta State, participated in the study. They include 48 males and 50 females accidentally sampled from their different lesson points using simple random sampling technique. Their religious affiliation and cultural background were not put into consideration as any persons who indicate interest or attracted were included in the study. Their age ranged between 13 to 20 with mean age of 15.30. The minimum educational attainment of the participants was SSCE or WAEC/NECO. Their tribes ethnicity and religious affiliation over not considered.

Instrument

The instrument used was a questionnaire which consists of two sections. The first section of the instrument contains demographic data or personal data such as age, gender, certificate obtained, parent career and educational level. The second section contains the questionnaire for Parental Career in Conduct Disorder (PCCD). The questionnaire was developed by Uria (2000) to measure parental career or vocation in youths conduct disorder. The scale contains 25 items, out of which 3 items measures the subscale which are arranged in likert format, ranging from strongly disagree 1 to strongly agree 5. Choa's (2001) found the scale to have total conbach alpha of .64 to .71. The research in a pilot study with 60 adolescents from Nigeria sample Toyin and Igbedioh (2002) found coefficient alpha of .70.

Procedure

Permission was obtained from the management of the lessons/extra moral studies and the various class mistress and master. In each extra moral class the participants filled an agreement form before he/she was allowed to participate in the study. All the participants selected for the study were gathered in their various extra moral class rooms and the questionnaire was administered to them with the help of the research assistants employed. The participants were given instructions on how to fill the questionnaire and it took an average of 30 minutes for all of them to be completed and all the questionnaire were collected immediately for scoring.

Design/Statistics

A cross sectional survey design was used for the study while 2 way ANOVA statistics was also use as a statistical package.

Results

The data obtained from the research instrument were analyzed using the 2 way ANOVA. The result of study showed significant differences on the manifestations of conduct disorder in both profession and educational variables respectively. However no interaction effect of the career and education on conduct disorder was observed.

Table 1: Summary table of mean score of the subscales profession and education

Score	Mean
Career	
Traders vocational	0.68
Workers	26.05
Civil servants	8.20
Education	2.07
Educated	
Non-educated	32.01

Table 2: Summary table of 2 way ANOVA of career and education on conduct disorder

Source	SS	DF	MS	F	SIG
Profession	7839.04	2	2391.52	65.89	Sig
Education	1098.11	1	1098.11	0.39	"
Pro + Edu	3115.62	2	1557.82	2.86	"
Error Edu	106835.20	196	545.08		"
Error Pro	273681.90	98	2792.67		"

The table above shows a significance at .05 level of the testing, table II above showed that career and education had significant effect on conduct disorder among young adults. However, no interaction effects were found. Judging from the mean table, young adult of traders and vocational workers had more conduct disorders than young adults of civil servant. On the other hand, young adults of the educated parents (having at least NCE) showed lesser conduct disorders than those of the non-educated parents.

Discussion

This work examined the influence of parental career and education on conduction disorder among young adults. One of the hypothesis postulated which stated that there will be no statistical significance difference among children of parents with diverse career was rejected. The children of traders showed more conduct disorder, followed by the children from parents of vocational manual workers then those of the civil servants who were educated. In essence educated, civil servants appeared to show high family standard and healthy upbringing than the others. The result may be attributed to the number and quality of time parents spent with their children and wards. Parents who are civil servants are more likely to spend quality time with their wards or young adults as well as quantity time. Their wards or young adults thus are moulded under the tutelage of a parent in certain aspects.

Thus this augurs well with Marsh and Wolf (2000) discussion of their studies. They concluded that presence of parents at home determined significantly the positive behaviour of young adult. Furthermore, this result may as well be explained from the position of exposure to conduct disordered environment. Children or young adult of the petty traders and vocational workers may be more likely to be exposed to risky environments for conduct disorder than those of the civil servant. They are more likely to help in their parents shops. At such, such children or young adults may be exposed to bad companies and unscrutinised relationship that may not augur well for their survival. They may learn so many ill - manned behaviours from orders persons around, from corrupt apprentices and other people that may not be examples of the true society. However, the mean result further explicated that the young adults of petty traders showed the most level of conduct disorder. Marketing and trading of young adult go with numerous hazards than imagined. The young adult could learn how to steal, chase women and commit all sought of misconduct. Such young adults may as well loose interest in their education and as such may constitute problem from the school management.

The other hypothesis postulated which stated that young adults of non-educated parents will statically significantly have more conduct disorder than young adult of educated and literate parents was accepted. The educated and literate parents appear to have better socio-economic standard and reasons well than non-educated parents. It has also been found that conduct disorder appears in less privileged or poor families more than in middle or upper class families. Here the socio-economic standard associated with educated parents might for that reason outshine the other groups. For this study, the following suggestions were deemed necessary for the management of young adult of those whose parents are petty traders and vocational workers whose job and services does not grant them opportunity of being present with their young adults all the time. Finding suggests that rational interaction with young adults often as possible to understand their developmental tasks and problems and offer solution some how helps alot. Taking time to know what the young adults are doing in school and being part of their personal world, as often as they are free always helps in settling the problem of deviance and conduct behaviour to a large extent.

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